

FINAL REPORT

SPOKE 1: MOUNTAIN INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM

PROJECT NAME: eco-friendly Innovation: agave Silk-basEd sUBstrates for next-generation Photovoltaic cells and printable electronics (RISE-UP)

The Final Report relates to the scientific activities carried out and the results achieved within the project funded through the Young Researcher Call for Proposals: it must provide a comprehensive description of the project results, with specific reference to the project activities carried out, the progress made and the achievement of the milestones and targets set out in the approved project.

The Final Report is submitted by the PI (principal investigator) and is evaluated by the Scientific Committee, in accordance with the provisions of the aforementioned Call for Proposals.

The Final Report must underscore these aspects:

- the final objectives achieved and set out in the project submitted for evaluation, as well as any deviations from the established objectives and the reasons for such deviations;
- any deviations between the approved Economic and Financial Plan and the reported costs, that must be justified.

PROJECT DETAILS	
Spoke	1 – Mountain Innovation Ecosystem
PROJECT ACRONYM	RISE-UP
PI – Principal Investigator - University	Manuela Ciocca
Starting date:	04/10/2024
Duration:	12 months
Ending date:	03/10/2025
<i>Other participants - university</i>	Prof. Franco Cacialli, Prof. Niko Stephan Münzenrieder, Michele Pompilio, Dr. Annelot Nijkoops

Annexes:

Possible annex	
Possible annex	

Date: --31.01.2026-----

PI signature: -----

1. Technical and scientific results of the project

1.1. Description of the final results achieved

Maximum two pages.

Images and diagrams may be attached at the end of the report. Indicate whether the expected results were achieved, explaining and quantifying any deviations.

Describe the expected and actual results of the project in qualitative terms.

The RISE-UP project successfully met its core objective: the development and validation of agave silk fiber (ASF)-based eco-friendly substrates for photovoltaic (PV) and printable electronics applications, particularly aligned with sustainability goals in mountain innovation ecosystems.

1. ASF Extraction and Substrate Fabrication

A sustainable ASF extraction protocol was developed using agave plants sourced from local Moroccan partners. Leaves were processed through a multi-step method involving drying, soaking, manual beating. The extracted fibres were grinded into a fine powder using a high-performance grinding system, then dissolved in deionized water to form a homogeneous suspension. Drop-casting techniques were optimized to deposit smooth, crack-free films. The resulting films showed uniform thickness and suitable surface quality for electronic use.

This phase concluded to the achievement of the **ML1 milestone: fabrication of high-quality ASF-based-eco-friendly-substrates.**

2. Substrate Characterization

Mechanical, morphological, and optical characterizations confirmed the suitability of ASF substrates for thin-film devices.

Mechanical tests revealed good tensile strength and flexibility, critical for flexible electronics.

SEM and confocal microscopy confirmed fibre homogeneity of the ASF-substrates.

Optical measurements showed transparency values exceeding 75%, fulfilling the targeted performance metrics.

Biodegradability tests indicated the substrate's breakdown under ambient and aqueous conditions, supporting the environmental sustainability claims.

These results enabled **ML2: characterization of the ASF-substrates, ensuring all the necessary specifications.**

3. Functional Prototypes

Resistive temperature sensors prototypes were successfully developed: ASF-based temperature sensors were fabricated via using printed silver-based conductive ink on ASF substrates and copper deposited on ASF-substrates via sputtering. These devices showed stable operation and mechanical resilience under mild deformation.

Environmental stability tests under temperature variations confirmed the robustness of the devices.

A phototransistor, full printed on ASF-substrates, has been also designed and fabricated, the device characterization (performance, biocompatibility and biodegradability) is still ongoing.

The realization of functional ASF-based electronic devices ensured the achievement of **ML3:**

Demonstrating the practical application of ASFs substrates through the development and testing of functional prototypes.

All key project objectives were achieved with no major deviations. The project delivered both scientific advances in substrate engineering and technological demonstrators supporting green electronics. In addition to the development of the ASF-based substrates, two classes of electronic prototypes were successfully fabricated and tested: thin-film temperature sensors (screen-printed and sputtered) and a phototransistor (currently under optimization). While fully operational organic photovoltaic (OPV) devices were not finalized within the project timeframe, the transparent ASF substrates demonstrated suitable optical, mechanical, and morphological properties for photovoltaic applications. These results confirm their compatibility with OPV architectures and define a clear path for future integration.

Overall, the outcomes of RISE-UP lay a solid foundation for further development, scale-up, and broader adoption of ASF-based substrates in the field of flexible, biodegradable, and sustainable electronics.

Highlight the starting and final TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and the main KPI (Key Performance Indicator) achieved

The RISE-UP project began with a **starting TRL of 2**, corresponding to basic technology research and concept formulation. **At the end of the project, the technology reached TRL 4**, having demonstrated functional lab-scale prototypes. Specifically, ASF-based substrates were integrated into two types of electronic demonstrators: temperature sensors (screen-printed and sputtered) and a phototransistor (under final optimization).

Main KPIs achieved:

- Substrate fabrication reproducibility: $\geq 80\%$ success rate in obtaining peelable, homogeneous films.
- Substrate transparency (400–800 nm): $\sim 82\%$ average, suitable for optoelectronic devices.
- Surface roughness (Rq): < 400 nm, adequate for printed electronics and thin-film deposition.
- Mechanical integrity: Maintained performance under bending radii down to 5 mm.
- Environmental impact: Confirmed biodegradability in DI water within 5–7 days.

Demonstrator functionality:

- Temperature sensors: Fully operational, linear response from 20–60 °C.
- Phototransistor: Partially functional, ongoing optimization.

These KPIs confirm the project's success in delivering a functional, biodegradable substrate platform for sustainable electronics.

The outcomes of the research project, along with collaborative efforts with partner research groups, resulted in the publication of **three conference papers** and **one peer-reviewed journal article**:

1. S. Krik et al., "Application of Agave Silk Fibers in Sustainable and Flexible Electronics," 2025 IEEE International Conference on Flexible and Printable Sensors and Systems (FLEPS), Singapore, 2025, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/FLEPS65444.2025.11105695.
2. M. Pompilio et al., "Time-Resolved Analysis of Near-Infrared Porphyrinbased OLEDs for Future Flexible Applications: A Study on Host-Guest Energy Transfer and Singlet (re)Generation From Triplets Mechanisms in Porphyrin-Based, Near-Infrared Emitting OLEDs, Providing Insight into Promising Candidates for Future Flexible Light-Emitting Devices," 2025 IEEE International Conference on Flexible and Printable Sensors and Systems (FLEPS), Singapore, 2025, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/FLEPS65444.2025.11105613.
3. M. Ciocca, S. Krik, M. Pompilio, J. S. Gharehbagh, L. Petti and F. Cacialli, "Conjugated Polymer Nanoparticles for Multifunctional Bioelectronics and Sensing P3ht:Pcbm-Nps Embedded in Peo Hydrogel," 2025 IEEE International Conference on Flexible and Printable Sensors and Systems (FLEPS), Singapore, 2025, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/FLEPS65444.2025.11105550.
4. Ciocca, M., Nijkoops, A., Trentini, G. et al. Harnessing biomaterials for advanced biosensor and bioelectronic devices development: From natural chromophores to biodegradable substrates and peptide-based detection of nanoplastics. MRS Advances 10, 986–993 (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.1557/s43580-025-01199-7>

5. M. Pompilio et al., "Indium-Gallium-Zinc-Oxide Based Semitransparent Electrodes on Flexible Substrates for Biodegradable Electronics," 2024 IEEE International Flexible Electronics Technology Conference (IFETC), Bologna, Italy, 2024, pp. 1-3, doi: 10.1109/IFETC61155.2024.10771880.

Describe the External Partners who collaborated, their contribution, and the possible synergies that may continue in the near future

The external partners contributed to the success of the RISE-UP project, offering both technical expertise and access to infrastructure for characterization and testing:

- Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK, Trento)

FBK supported the mechanical characterization of the developed agave silk fiber (ASF)-based substrates. Their contributions included tensile strength and flexibility testing using advanced instrumentation, providing quantitative validation of the substrate's mechanical properties. Continued collaboration is foreseen, particularly for reliability testing and integration into multifunctional device stacks.

- Sensing Technology Laboratory (STL) Group, Free University of Bozen-Bolzano

STL contributed to the development of the printing methods for printable electronics. Future collaborations may include co-development of sensor integration strategies and support in biodegradability assessments.

- Flexible Electronics Laboratory (FEL) Group, Free University of Bozen-Bolzano

FEL contributed to surface morphology studies using confocal microscopy and assisted in understanding surface roughness parameters relevant for printable electronics. Furthermore, FEL contributed to the deposition of copper conductive materials on ASF-substrates.

- CHOSE - Centre for Hybrid and Organic Solar Energy

CHOSE contributed to the development of ASF-substrates for OPV devices indicating the necessary transparency and roughness requirements. Future collaborations will include co-development and characterization of OPV devices on ASF-based substrates.

1.2. Summary of deliverables

Name	Result ¹	Links	TRL ²	Description and references
	[SCI] [PROD] [SERV] [PROC] [BUS] [DSG] [METH] [PO]	Link to Zenodo or BIA	[TRL4] [TRL5] [TRL6] [TRL7] [TRL8] [N.A.]	[Publication] [Prototyping in laboratory environment] [Prototyping in production environment] [Pilot, demonstrator or test] [Intellectual property management] [Patent submission] [Other]
ASF-based substrate	[PROD]		TRL4	Prototyping in laboratory environment: Biodegradable substrate fabricated from agave silk fibers; mechanically and morphologically characterized
Printed temperature sensor	[PROD]		TRL5	Prototyping in lab: Flexible temperature sensor printed on ASF substrate; functional and stable under mild deformation.
Phototransistor prototype (ongoing)	[PROD]		TRL4	Prototyping in laboratory: Initial fabrication of optoelectronic device on ASF substrate; testing underway.
Transparent substrate for OPV	[PROD]		TRL4	Proof of concept: ASF-substrate demonstrated >80% transparency in visible range, suitable for integration with OPV devices.
Biodegradability test	[SCI] [DSG] [METH]		N.A.	Biodegradability platform: Degradation in DI water monitored by electrical measurements and video/photos recording
Poster and oral presentations	[PO]		N.A.	Dissemination: Poster presented at RESORB/2025 iNEST meetings and oral talk at FLEPS 2025 and iNEST meetings.
Conference papers (x3) + journal (x1)	[SCI]		N.A.	Publication: Dissemination of research results; topics covered: fabrication, characterization, and sustainability.

¹ [SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory, etc.] [PROD — Product (new or improved)] [SERV — Service (new or improved)] [PROC — Industrial process (new or improved)] [BUS — Business model (new or improved)] [DSG — Design (new or improved)] [METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)]

² [TRL4 - Technology validated in the laboratory] [TRL5 - Technology validated in the relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment] [TRL7 - Demonstration of the prototype system in an operational environment] [TRL8 - Complete and qualified system] [TRL9 - Real system tested in an operational environment] [Not applicable]

2. COMPLIANCE WITH CONDITIONALITIES AND ALL ADDITIONAL REQUIREMENTS RELATED TO THE PNRR MEASURES

2.1. DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code

Description of how the activities carried out comply with the DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code. In this regard, the reasons why the activities carried out do not cause significant harm to each of the environmental objectives are reported.

Environment	Has the DNSH principle been respected for the environmental objective? (Y/N) ³	Justifications:
1. Climate change mitigation	Y	The project promotes biodegradable and renewable materials (ASF) as alternatives to rigid, inorganic or plastic based substrates, reducing the carbon footprint of electronics.
2. Climate change adaptation	Y	Although not directly targeting climate adaptation, the project supports sustainable materials suitable for fragile ecosystems (e.g., mountains) without negative impact.
3. Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources	Y	No significant impact. Water used in processing was limited and reused where applicable. No pollutants were discharged into aquatic systems.
4. Transition to a circular economy, including waste reduction and recycling	Y	ASF substrates are biodegradable and derived from agave leaves, an agricultural by-product, supporting circularity and reducing e-waste.
5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution	Y	No polluting chemicals were used. The process avoided solvents or materials with known air, water, or soil contamination risks.
6. Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystem	Y	Agave harvesting was small-scale, non-invasive, and done in coordination with local cooperatives, ensuring no impact on biodiversity or natural habitats.

2.2. Consistency with the digital constraint

Max 500 characters

³ If the activities carried out do not have an impact on the environmental objective, it is appropriate to answer "Yes", in case of "Not", enter the reasons in the "Justifications" column of the same table..

The project supports the digital transition by developing biodegradable substrates for printed electronics, enabling the fabrication of eco-friendly sensors and flexible devices. These contribute to sustainable digital technologies, aligning with the EU's digital objectives while ensuring low environmental impact.

3. ECONOMICS RESULTS OF THE PROJECT

3.1. Project costs

Attach the final statement of costs incurred in connection with the project, indicating the type of cost incurred.

BUDGET	Final amount (€ - %)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
Costs for specialist consultancy services	9300,00 € - 17%	10000,00 € - 20%	This small modification was necessary to finalize a customized set up for biodegradability test. The change was formally justified in the re-budgeting request.
Costs for materials, supplies and similar products	35255,00 € - 70%	33960,00 € - 68%	This modification was necessary to acquire essential equipment required for the successful finalization of the project. The change was formally justified in the re-budgeting request.
Mission expenses	5400,00 € - 11%	5995,00 € - 12%	This modification was necessary for the successful dissemination of the research project 's results. The change was formally justified in the re-budgeting request.
Total	49955,00 €		

BUDGET	Final amount (€ - %)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
RI -	28174,00 € - 56.4%	21445,5 € - 43%	This modification was necessary to acquire essential equipment required for the successful finalization of the project, ensuring the achievement of the project objectives within the planned timeframe. The change was formally justified in the re-budgeting request, which was duly approved, and the distribution between Industrial Research (RI) and Experimental Development (SS) was preserved in full conformity with the requirements of the funding call.
SS -	21781,00 € - 43.6%	28509,5 € - 57%	This modification was necessary to acquire essential equipment required for the successful finalization of the project, ensuring the achievement of the project objectives within the planned timeframe. The change was formally justified in the re-budgeting request, which was duly approved, and the distribution between Industrial Research (RI) and Experimental Development (SS) was preserved in full conformity with the requirements of the funding call.
Total	49955,00 €		

4. SUMMARY OF TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC CHANGES TO THE PROJECT (IF ANY)

Summarise the technical and financial changes that have been made to the project. Please note that, according to the call for proposals, changes must not substantially alter the objectives, results and impact of the initial project and must not lead to an increase in total expenditure. Please also specify whether the changes have an impact on the balance between the different types of expenditure.

During the project implementation, minor technical changes were introduced that did not substantially alter the objectives, expected results, or overall impact of the RISE-UP project. Specifically, two printed electronic devices, namely temperature sensors, were successfully developed and tested on ASF-based substrates. Additionally, the fabrication of a phototransistor was initiated and is currently undergoing optimization for complete characterization. Although OPV devices were not finalized within the project timeframe, the core objective, which is the optimization of ASF substrates, was fully achieved. Notably, transparent ASF films with over 80% transmittance in the visible range were successfully developed, validating their applicability in future OPV devices.

On the financial side, a formal re-budgeting request was submitted and approved. The changes consisted solely of internal reallocations between budget categories, involving only marginal adjustments. These were essential to acquire specific equipment necessary for the completion of the project within the planned timeline. The reallocation was justified and accepted without impacting the total expenditure or altering the balance between different types of costs. Crucially, the distribution between Industrial Research (RI) and Experimental Development (SS) was preserved in full compliance with the call's requirements. All project objectives were met as initially defined, and the overall results and impact were achieved as planned.